

ROLE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8432237>

Abstract. *This article discusses the requirements for the use of digital technologies and Internet resources in the process of teaching foreign languages. In particular, it highlights the importance of systematic selection of teaching aids to achieve specific goals set by the teacher.*

Keywords: *modern education, computerization, digital technologies, selection of teaching aids, foreign language, modern classrooms.*

Everyone knows that language is a means of interaction, communication, and thought. For the peoples of the world, their mother tongue is their priceless value, the pride of the nation. Language is the consciousness and memory, psyche, spiritual and cultural image, national values, and past of the nation. The role of language in the development of the nation, state, and society is very important, necessary and urgent. As the nation, state, and society progress, his love and attention to the language increases. Progress in social life determines progress in language.

The progress of time has increased attention to languages. Perfect learning of not only the mother tongue, but also foreign languages has become the demand of the times. In the era of information technologies, excellent knowledge of a foreign language has become one of the main requirements for high professional qualifications. It is not for nothing that special attention is paid to learning the languages of international communication. The education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is rising to a new level of quality based on the introduction of new information and communication and pedagogical technologies that can fully meet the requirements of the time, based on a scientific approach.

All conditions and opportunities have been created for the education of the growing young generation in a comprehensive manner, for their thorough acquisition of modern knowledge and professions. During these reforms, special attention was paid to the teaching of foreign languages. In this regard, today it was established that a document showing the level of knowledge of any foreign language is required from every representative of the young generation who wants to continue their education at a higher educational institution or after education.

Also, within the framework of the adoption of the decision "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" adopted during the past years and the implementation of this document, the material and technical base of language rooms of general education schools was strengthened. In such classes, students are taught lessons based on modern technologies. Foreign language lessons are taught using multimedia from the 1st grade. Classrooms in modern renovated secondary schools are equipped with video projectors, television, computer, visual aids and didactic toys. Polish became the basis for this, since learning science in a playful way with the help of educational video programs, cartoons, as well as pictures, songs and poems helps to master the educational material. As a result, students quickly master the colloquial language and strengthen their knowledge through stage shows performed in a foreign language. Today, almost all schoolchildren know a foreign language to one degree or another. In fact, the vocabulary of first graders is about 60 words and phrases. It should be noted that the seminars,

open classes and their discussion held in schools for the purpose of improving the qualifications of foreign language teachers make it possible to popularize the most advanced pedagogical practices. Taking into account the requirements of the times, such popularization works are implemented today with the help of information communication tools and computer technologies.

One of the distinctive features of the era is the rapid development of information and communication technologies, using its capabilities, and paying special attention to a new approach to the educational process and its organization. The 21st century is the age of high computer technologies, and modern young people are taking steps not only in accordance with the spirit of the time, but also in accordance with the progress in the electronic world. For this reason, a different approach to the process of educating the younger generation is required. The role of the teacher in the lessons is also changing. The teacher now acts mainly as a guide. It is time for teachers who aim to keep pace with the times to be ready to revive any part of the lesson through information and communication technologies.

In order to adequately protect the country's honor in the world arena, our youth must first be able to compete with their foreign peers. Today, the competition is conducted in foreign languages. In fact, the role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in the purposeful organization of didactic game-type lessons that are interesting to students is very important in improving the quality and efficiency of education. The possibilities of their use are expanding day by day, and technical tools are becoming an integral part of the educational process. In order to teach young people a foreign language through a computer, first of all, the teacher himself must be able to use computer technologies at a professional level. The use of this level includes not only the ability to fully use the available capabilities of the computer, but also the ability to organize new educational programs based on it. And in order to become a skilled foreign language pedagogue, every foreign language teacher should work more on himself in the field of modern technologies.

Because teaching a foreign language through a computer has several advantages over traditional teaching methods. First of all, a student learning a foreign language on the basis of a computer will have a wider opportunity to test the four skills of the language, that is, the skills of reading, listening, writing and speaking. Today, with the help of developed programs, the number of possibilities for this is very large and wide. It is only necessary to be able to properly direct the student to this method of education. In addition, it has been proven that every rule, every word, every unit of concept taught in the teaching of foreign languages with the help of computer technologies is better kept in the student's memory. In fact, the rich graphic capabilities of the computer, that is, the ability to deliver information in the form of voice, text and video images, have made computer teaching of foreign languages one of the most effective methods.

The main purpose of using modern technologies in learning foreign languages is to facilitate easy learning of science. In this case, the opportunities to listen and understand a certain source, express it in speech, read and understand, and express it in writing expand.

An important factor in the pedagogical process is the implementation of teaching on the basis of modern technologies oriented to the individual. This method helps to improve work efficiency. Teachers can use their students' free and creative time to develop themselves.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of information technologies, more precisely, the effective and appropriate use of computer technologies in universities and secondary schools, opens the door to more learning and research for a student learning a foreign language. Also, the

use of computer technologies in learning and teaching a foreign language makes the work of both the student and the teacher much easier. It can be seen that the use of information and communication tools, computer technologies in the educational processes of teaching foreign languages and in extracurricular (independent) work creates wide opportunities for students of almost all ages, and thus makes it possible to compensate for insufficient lessons per week will give.

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